

Carpet with Good Indoor Air Quality – A Technical Appraisal

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Abstract

Indoor air quality is of prime importance for good human health. In addition to the indoor activities such as cooking, cleaning, painting, smoking etc, the quality of air in indoor area is also affected by the type of furnishing used in the interior. In this respect, role of carpet is very crucial. The current write up elaborates the importance of indoor air quality on human health. It points out the possibility of air pollutants associated with the carpets. The write up also mentions few international regulatory bodies for certifying the sustainability and environmental performance of the carpets. It also highlights the corrective actions to be taken to minimise the problem of indoor air quality associated with the installation of carpets.

Keywords: Carpet, Dust mites, Indoor air quality (IAQ), Nylon, Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)

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1. Introduction

Normally, human beings spend more than 80% time of their daily life in an indoor environment. Therefore, the indoor environment has a significant impact on human health [1]. The quality of air in and around a closed premise is commonly known as Indoor air quality (IAQ). It relates to the health, comfort and well being of occupants residing within the premise [2].

It has been observed that the Indoor air pollution within a building or a structure might be 10 times worse than outdoor air pollution [3]. One of the major reasons to happen this is that as compared to the open spaces, the contained area can permit pollutants to build up more.

Statisticians suggest that in developing countries, health impacts of indoor air pollution is far outweigh to those of outdoor air pollution. The National Health & Medical Research Council (NHMRC) of Australia defines indoor air as air within a building occupied for at least one hour by people of varying states of health [4]. This can include the office, classroom, transport, hotel, hospital & home. The major indoor air pollutants are emissions from carpet, particulate matter, carbon monoxide, second-hand tobacco smoke, pesticides, solvents, mites, allergies, moulds, occupation-related contaminants etc [5]. Indoor air quality can be influenced by outdoor air quality also, viz. Industrial or agricultural activities, treatment of industrial effluents and domestic residues, traffic, solid waste management, chemical incidents & spills etc.

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Carpet contributes to functionalities like thermal and sound insulation. In addition to this, it enhances the walking comfort and aesthetics of the floor [6]. In the present study, attempt is made to identify the chemicals used during the carpet manufacture, which may affect the indoor air quality. The regulating bodies involved in maintaining good IAQ has also been brought into light through this precise technical appraisal.

2. Vulnerability of poor IAQ on breathing

Pediatric children have a higher resting metabolic rate as compared to adults because they are growing rapidly. Similarly, their rate of oxygen consumption per unit body weight is also higher than adults because they have a larger surface area per unit body weight. This is one of the reasons, why the exposure to any air pollutant to pediatric infants is greater [7].

In addition to this, pediatric infants have narrower airways than adults. This may cause a comparatively severe irritation and obstruction in the airways of a young child due to any air pollutant [8]. The figure shown depicts the above facts:

Figure 1 - Effect of Edema on the cross-sectional area of Airway for Adult & Pediatric

The effect of edema on the adult airway is much less dramatic than it is on the newborn's airway. One millimeter of edema

reduces the diameter of the adult airway by about 19%, whereas it reduces the diameter of the infant airway by 56%.

3. Pollutants of carpet

3.1 Emission of VOC and absorption of gases on to the surface of Carpet

Many house hold items such as Plywood furniture, plastics, glues/adhesives and paints emit formaldehyde, styrene, benzene and many harmful volatile solvents respectively [9,10]. Carpets, particularly tufted carpets also emit Volatile organic compounds (VOCs). SBR backing latex of tufted carpet is very odorous and therefore readily detected by smell. VOCs are also generated during installation of wall to wall carpets, especially when direct stick or glue-down systems are used for installation. In fact, conventional solvent-based adhesives emit substantial amount of VOCs during drying stage of installation. Hence, these adhesives are now being replaced by the new low-emission adhesives.

Interestingly, carpets made of woollen yarn have ability to absorb gases out of the atmosphere, particularly combustion gases. In an experiment, various surfaces were exposed to sulphur dioxide-contaminated air and the ability of the surfaces to absorb the sulphur dioxide (SO₂) was measured [11]. The results are depicted in Table 3.1:-

Table 1 - Amount of Sulphur Dioxide absorbed by various surfaces

Type of surface	Amount of Sulphur Dioxide (mg/m ²)	
	after 30 minutes	after 1 hour
Varnished wood	0.11	0.11
Painted wall	0.13	0.13
Cork floor	0.36	0.36
Fibre-board ceiling	0.53	0.99
Softwood	1.70	2.82
Wool fabric	1.85	3.46

It is evident from Table 3.1 that majority of the hard surfaces quickly get saturated, but wool is particularly good at absorbing SO₂. In a different experiment, SO₂ was applied to textile fibres. Figure 3.1 displays the results for two common fibres used in carpet pile surfaces: wool and nylon. This demonstrates how wool absorbs SO₂ for a far longer period of time than nylon, which becomes saturated very quickly. Both formaldehyde and nitrous oxides can be effectively absorbed by wool fibres. Testing by the Wool Research Organisation of New Zealand (WRONZ) involved exposing wool and nylon carpets separately to environments contaminated by high concentrations of NO₂ in environmental chambers.

Compared to the nylon carpet, the wool carpet reduced the concentration of NO₂ gas far more quickly and to a much lower level, as seen in Figure 3.2. It is pertinent to mention that in woollen carpet, the absorbed gas did not get re-emit in the atmosphere at later stage [12-14].

Figure 2 - Comparison of Sulphur dioxide absorption rates (g SO₂ per 100 mg sample per minute) for wool and nylon, exposed to 2.92 g per L SO₂ at an air-flow of 1L per min

Figure 3 - Comparison of wool and nylon carpets in terms of ability to reduce the concentration of nitrogen dioxide in indoor air

3.2 Accumulation of dust on to the surface of Carpet

All respiratory distress associated with asthma is most commonly caused by dust mite antigens, which are present in house and construction dust. Moulds, algae, pollen, and plant spores are other airborne particle and dust-related causes of asthma. The primary allergen in household dust is the dust mite or dermatophagoides pteronyssinus. Skin flakes are generally the source of nutrients for these dustmites. Low dust levels should be maintained in situations when allergy reactions are caused by dust sensitization [15]. Wool is ranked second in the Triboelectric series, behind nylon. This indicates that, as compared to other carpet-grade fibres (like acrylic, polyester, polypropylene or silk), wool has a far lower attraction to dust particles. The following were the findings of a study conducted by the German Applied and Experimental Allergy Research Association (GAF) titled "Allergies in Carpets":-

- Dust mites prefer to reside on human skin flakes instead of textile materials, which are naturally found in carpets lying indoors.
- The ideal growth conditions for mites and fungal moulds are between 18-25 °C and 60-70 % relative humidity.
- Dust mites dry out and die in humidity levels below 50%

RH; in humidity levels exceeding 70% RH, fungal moulds destroy them.

- The dust mites may be quickly eradicated using rigorous cleaning or disinfection methods.

Research has unequivocally demonstrated that, under normal conditions, carpets do not provide a specific risk since they do not promote the formation of dust mites. It has been demonstrated that wool carpets outperform synthetic ones when it comes to preventing dust mite infection.

4. International regulatory bodies for sustainability certification and environmental performance of carpets

4.1 Australian Environmental Certification scheme (ECS)

The Australian Carpet Classification Scheme (ACCS) is a national carpet grading scheme. An extension of this is the Environmental Certification Scheme (ECS), which offers guidance on the environmental performance of carpet. Among other things, ECS-certified carpet manufacturers must adhere to a code of practice that details performance standards for raw materials, manufacturing, in-service use and end-of-life treatment.

4.2 UL GREENGUARD Gold Certification

Products awarded the GREENGUARD Gold Certification by UL Environment are subject to advanced dynamic environmental chamber testing, along with exposure modeling and analytical measurements, to ensure they do not contain more than stipulated levels of VOCs, formaldehyde, ozone and phthalates. The certification tests for suitability of the use of these products by sensitive individuals such as children and the elderly.

4.3 NSF/ANSI 140 – Gold Certified NSF/ANSI 140

Sustainability Assessment for Carpet is a U.S. national standard that measures and certifies the sustainability of commercial carpets based on lifecycle assessment principles.

4.4 Singapore Green Labeling Scheme (SGLS)

The Singapore Green Labeling Scheme (SGLS), administered by the Singapore Environment Council, endorses industrial consumer products that are environmentally responsible.

4.5 The Carpet and Rug Institute (CRI) Green Label Plus

The Carpet and Rug Institute Green Label Plus program sets

a high standard for indoor air quality by certifying products with very low levels of volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions. As a prerequisite for initial certification, carpets must undergo a 14-day testing process as directed by California's Section 01350, a standard practice for VOC Testing. Carpet & Rug Institute (CRI) defines the Green Label Plus criteria of Emissions for Specific Compounds.

4.6 Steps to minimise problems and to improve carpeted IAQ

Suitable actions should be taken to minimise problems associated with the installation of carpet [16].

- Low emission level of carpets and underlay(s) should be ensured from manufacturers.
- The building should be well ventilated, where the carpet is to be installed.
- The adhesives / backing material to be used for manufacturing carpet should have specification of lowest VOC emission levels.
- The surrounding area of the building should be free from unusual high Suspended particulate matter (SPM), dust gases etc.
- Ventilation in the room should be continued for 2-3 days after the carpet is installed.
- Vacuum cleaner of appropriate commercial specification should be used with fine particle filters to prevent redistribution of contaminated air into the atmosphere.
- For any complaint about odour or other alleged physiological reactions arise, then steps should be taken to investigate it without assuming that the carpet is at fault.

5. Conclusion

The main goal of this assessment is to shed light on the horrifying effects of VOCs, gases, chemicals, mites and other allergens on indoor air quality in presence of carpet. Thus all stake holders including carpet users, manufacturers, buyers, sellers, nodal agencies etc. can be boasted of an awareness to maintain a high indoor air quality through carpets for healthy living. Hence necessary initiatives are imminent to make the indoor air quality as pollution free. Carpet being an artefact of visual, walking & acoustic comfort, let's manufacture it as a pollution free product of 21st century.

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